

LONG-TERM LIFE PREDICTION OF QUASI-ISOTROPIC CFRP LAMINATES WITH A HOLE UNDER COMPRESSIVE LOADING

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SUMMARY

This paper is concerned with the long-term life prediction of CFRP laminates with a hole under compressive loading based on the accelerated testing methodology (ATM) combined with the micromechanics of failure (MMF). The reliability of MMF/ATM methodology is discussed by comparing the predicted results with the experimental ones.

Keywords: Polymer composites, Life prediction, Accelerated testing, Micromechanics of failure

INTRODUCTION

The accelerated testing methodology (ATM) [1] was proposed for the prediction of long-term fatigue strength of CFRP laminates based on the time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP). Based on ATM, the long-term fatigue strength for CFRP laminates and structures can be predicted by measuring the short-term fatigue strengths at elevated temperatures. The applicability of ATM was confirmed for CFRP laminates and structures combined with PAN based carbon fibers and thermosetting resins [2-4]. Furthermore, the formulation for the master curves of time-temperature dependent fatigue strength was performed based on Christensen's theory [5] which describes statistically the crack kinetics in viscoelastic body. The failure criteria of separated fiber and matrix in polymer composites have been developed and the failure of composite structures has been predicted based on the analyses on micromechanics, laminates and structure levels. Recently, stress-based micromechanics of failure (MMF) have been proposed by Christensen for polymer composite with viscoelastic matrix.

In this paper, the constituent-based prediction of long-term strength of CFRP structure by combined MMF/ATM approach is studied. The time-temperature dependent master curves of MMF/ATM constituent-based critical parameters are constructed according to constant strain rate (CSR) tests for four directions of unidirectional CFRP under various temperatures and measuring the time-temperature shift factor for viscoelastic behavior

of transverse CFRP laminates. The long term open hole compression (OHC) strength of quasi-isotropic CFRP laminate under CSR loading is predicted using the master curves of MMF/ATM critical parameters based on MMF/ATM combined method.

MMF/ATM PROCEDURE

The outline of MMF/ATM approach is shown schematically in Figure 1. The MMF/ATM procedure includes, (a) the viscoelastic modulus in the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP is measured at various temperatures. The master curve and the time-temperature shift factor are determined by using these test data based on the TTSP. (b) The CSR strengths in the typical four directions of unidirectional CFRP are measured at various temperatures at a single loading rate. The four directions are the longitudinal tension (X) and compression (X') and transverse tension (Y) and compression (Y'), respectively. (c) The master curves of these strengths are determined by using the measured data and the time-temperature shift factor for viscoelastic modulus. (d) The master curves of four MMF/ATM critical parameters, fiber tensile strength T_f , fiber compressive strength C_f , matrix tensile strength T_m , and matrix compressive strength C_m are determined through the method described in [6].

With the master curves of the MMF/ATM critical parameters, long-term strength prediction of CFRP becomes possible. Two-step stress analyses are necessary to process the test result, including stress analysis for “homogenous” CFRP laminate or structure in macro level and stress analysis for the constituents in micro level by stress amplification. From the master curves of MMF/ATM critical parameters and failure criteria for fiber and matrix, the strength of CFRP laminate or structure under arbitrary time to failure and temperature can be determined.

Figure 1 MMF/ATM procedure of prediction of long-term fatigue strength of polymer composites under arbitrary frequency, stress ratio and temperature

EXPERIMENTS

The test specimens were fabricated from unidirectional CFRP and quasi-isotropic CFRP laminate (QIL) $[45/0/-45/90]_{2s}$ of MR60H/1053 which consists MR60H carbon fiber and epoxy resin 1053. The unidirectional CFRP were used to back-calculate the constituent properties. The QIL was used for strength prediction verification. All the laminates were made by the autoclave technique. The curing procedure includes 180°C for 2 hours and then postcured at 160°C for 70 hours. The volume fraction of fiber is approximately 0.55. The laminates were cut by diamond-grit wheel to the specific size for the tests. The dynamic viscoelastic tests were performed for various frequencies and temperatures for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP. The shift factors for constructing master curve hold for strength master curve of CFRP and constituent critical parameters' master curves. The CSR tests for four directions of unidirectional CFRP were carried out to extract constituent critical parameters' master curves by micromechanical amplification. Longitudinal and transverse CSR tension tests at various temperatures were carried out according with JIS K7073 to get the longitudinal and transverse tensile CSR strengths X and Y , respectively. Longitudinal and transverse CSR compression tests at various temperatures were carried out according with SACMA SRM1R-94 and JIS K7076, respectively, to get the longitudinal and transverse compressive CSR strengths X' and Y' , respectively. The OHC CSR tests for QIL under various temperatures were carried out as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Open hole compression (OHC) tests for QIL

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Creep Compliance of Matrix Resin

The left side of Figure 4 shows the master curve of the storage modulus E' for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP versus time t , where time t is the inverse of frequency. The right side shows the master curve of E' which is constructed by shifting E' at various constant temperatures along the logarithmic scale of t and logarithmic scale of E' until they overlapped each other, for the reduced time t' at the reference temperature $T_0=34^{\circ}\text{C}$. Since E' at various constant temperatures can be superimposed so that a smooth curve is constructed, the TTSP is applicable for the storage modulus

for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP. The time-temperature shift factor $a_{T_0}(T)$ which is the horizontal shift amount shown in Figure 5(a) can be formulated by the following equation

$$\log a_{T_0}(T) = \frac{\Delta H_1}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) H(T_g - T) + \left[\frac{\Delta H_1}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) H(T_g - T) + \frac{\Delta H_2}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_g} \right) \right] (1 - H(T_g - T)), \quad (1)$$

where G is the gas constant, 8.314×10^{-3} [kJ/(K•mol)], ΔH_1 and ΔH_2 are the activation energies below and above the glass transition temperature T_g , respectively, and H is the Heaviside step function. The temperature shift factor, $b_{T_0}(T)$, which is the amount of vertical shift, shown in Figure 5(b) can be fit with the following equation

$$\log b_{T_0}(T) = b_1(T - T_0)H(T_g - T) + [b_1(T_g - T_0) + b_2(T - T_g)](1 - H(T_g - T)), \quad (2)$$

where b_1 and b_2 are the slopes of two line segments below and above T_g , respectively.

The creep compliance D_c of matrix resin was back-calculated from the storage modulus E' for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP using

$$D_c(t) = \varepsilon(t) / \sigma_0, \quad (3)$$

and a modified rule of mixture by Tsai and Hahn [7] as

$$\frac{1}{E_T} = \frac{1}{(1 + V_y^*)} \left[\frac{1}{E_{fT}} + \frac{V_y^*}{E_m} \right], \quad V_y^* = \eta_y \frac{V_m}{V_f}, \quad \eta_y = 0.516 \quad (4)$$

where E_m and E_{fT} are Young's modulus of matrix resin and transverse modulus of fiber, respectively, and V_f is the volume fraction of fibers. The master curve of back-calculated D_c of matrix resin is shown in Figure 6. The master curve of D_c can be formulated by the following equation

$$\log D_c = \log D_{c,0}(t'_0, T_0) + \log \left[\left(\frac{t'}{t'_0} \right)^{m_g} + \left(\frac{t'}{t'_g} \right)^{m_r} \right], \quad (5)$$

where $D_{c,0}$ is the creep compliance at reference time t'_0 and temperature T_0 , and t'_g is the glassy reduced time on T_0 , and m_g and m_r are the gradients in glassy and rubbery regions of D_c master curve. Parameters obtained from the formulations for $a_{T_0}(T)$, $b_{T_0}(T)$, and D_c are listed in Table I.

Figure 4 Master curve of storage modulus for transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP

(a) Time-temperature shift factor (b) Temperature shift factor

Figure 5 Shift factors of the storage modulus for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP

Figure 6 Master curve of creep compliance for matrix resin calculated from the storage modulus for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP

Table I Parameters for master curve of creep compliance for matrix resin

T_0 [°C]	25
D_{c0} [1/GPa]	0.302
t'_0 [min]	1
m_g	0.015
m_r	0.265
t'_g [min]	3.0×10^7
ΔH_1 [kJ/mol]	125
ΔH_2 [kJ/mol]	690
T_g [°C]	177
b_1	5.44×10^{-4}
b_2	-9.0×10^{-4}

Master Curves of MMF/ATM Critical Parameters

Figure 7 shows the CSR strengths for longitudinal tension X , longitudinal compression X' , transverse tension Y and transverse compression Y' versus temperature for unidirectional CFRP. From the time-temperature shift factors a_{T_0} shown in Figure 5(a), the CSR strength data obtained at various temperatures were transferred in CSR strength for the reduced time to failure t' at a reference temperature T_0 using

$$t' = \frac{t}{a_{T_0}(T)} \quad (6)$$

where t is the failure time. The master curves of CSR strengths for X , X' , Y and Y' versus the reduced time t' were formulated statistically with Weibull distribution theory by

$$\log \sigma_s(t', T_0) = \log \sigma_{s,0}(t'_0, T_0) + \frac{1}{\alpha} \log \left[-\ln(1 - P_f) \right] - n_r \log \left[\frac{D_c(t'/2, T_0)}{D_c(t'_0, T_0)} \right] \quad (7)$$

where, $\sigma_{s,0}$ is the CSR strength at the initial reduced time t'_0 at a reference temperature T_0 , n_r is the gradient in rubbery region of the CSR strength master curve, and n_r means the time and temperature dependence on the reduction of CSR strength. The parameters of $\sigma_{s,0}$ and n_r in the formula are determined by curve fitting. P_f is the failure probability and α_s is the shape parameter in CSR strength which is defined by the Weibull plots. The nonlinear statistical analysis was carried to obtain the parameter $\sigma_{s,0}$ and n_r by searching the maximum α_s . Figure 8 shows the formulated master curves of CSR strengths and the weibull distribution for scattering of X , X' , Y and Y' . The MMF/ATM critical parameter master curves T_f , C_f , T_m and C_m are shown in Figure 9. The critical parameter of T_f was back-calculated from the tensile CSR strength X . The X can be decided for specific time by the formulation. This process was repeated to construct other critical parameter master curves, the X' , Y and Y' yielding the critical parameters C_f , T_m and C_m , respectively.

Figure 7 CSR strength versus temperature for unidirectional CFRP

Figure 8 Master curves of CSR strength for unidirectional CFRP

Figure 9 Master curves of MMF/ATM critical parameters

Prediction of OHC Strengths for QIL

As an example of application of MMF/ATM critical parameters master curves, long-term OHC strength for QIL was predicted. Figure 10 shows the initial failure mechanism for CSR loading by comparing the failure indexes of MMF/ATM parameters under, for example, $T=25^{\circ}\text{C}$. k_{Tf} is failure index of fiber under tension, k_{Cf} is failure index of fiber under compression, and k_{Tm^*} is failure index of matrix under tension, and k_{Cm^*} is failure index of matrix under compression [6]. When one of these failure indexes reaches to unity, the initial failure of laminate occurs. The OHC failure of QIL under CSR loading was triggered by fiber compressive failure in 0° layer. For all temperature conditions tested, the same failure was observed with the above simulation. Therefore, the predicted master curves of OHC strength for QIL were constructed based on the MMF/ATM parameter of compressive strength of fiber. Figure 11 shows the predicted master curve of OHC strength for QIL with experimental data. The predicted strength is lower than the experimental data for all region of time to failure t' . Figure 12 shows the initial failure of OHC for QIL observed from the specimen in which the OHC test was stopped at 98% level of maximum stress under $T=25^{\circ}\text{C}$. The microbuckling of fiber in 0° layer as well as the transverse crack in 45° layer are observed. In the -45° and 90° layers, any failures can not be observed. Furthermore, any failures can not be observed for the specimen in which the OHC test was stopped at 95% stress level of maximum stress under all temperatures tested. Figure 13 shows the longitudinal compressive strength X' measured by using QIL specimen. The X' measured by using QIL specimen are higher than those measured by using unidirectional CFRP. It can be considered from this fact that the longitudinal compressive strength of 0° layer in QIL is reinforced by neighboring layers. The predicted OHC strength for QIL using X' measured from QIL agrees well with experimental data for all region of time to failure as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 10 Judgment of initial failure of OHC for QIL ($T=25^{\circ}\text{C}$, $t'=1$ min)

Figure 11 Predicted OHC strength for QIL

(a) 45° layer

(b) 0° layer

(c) -45° layer

(d) 90° layer

Figure 12 Observation of initial failure of OHC for QIL

($\sigma_{max}=0.98\sigma_s$, $T=25^{\circ}\text{C}$, $V=0.1\text{mm/min}$)

Figure 13 CSR strength versus temperature for X'

Figure 14 Predicted OHC strength for QIL from QIL

CONCLUSION

The time-temperature dependent master curves of MMF/ATM critical parameters were constructed for CFRP laminates MR60H/1053 by tensile and compressive tests under CSR loading for the longitudinal and transverse directions of unidirectional CFRP under various temperatures based on the time-temperature superposition principle which holds for the viscoelastic behavior of matrix resin. It was confirmed experimentally that the long-term OHC strength of quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates $[45/0/-45/90]_{2S}$ can be predicted using these master curves of MMF/ATM critical parameters considering the strengthening of compressive strength of carbon fiber by neighboring layers.

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